

Table 1. Variability in 53 Ghaiya varieties for different traits.

Character	Range	Mean	SD	SE
Leaf length (cm)	16-85	50.2	9.77	0.42
Leaf width (cm)	1-2.6	1.61	0.25	0.01
Leaves tallest tiller ⁻¹ (no.)	4-8	5.58	0.85	2.22
Internode length (cm)	29-47	38.57	3.0	0.29
Culms (no.)	1-14	4.99	2.39	0.10
Plant height (cm)	80-156	133.0	11.28	1.10
Panicle length (cm)	20.3-28	24.59	1.49	0.15
Grains tallest tillers ⁻¹ (no.)	3-332	110.2	50.97	0.04

Indigenous ghaiya varieties have a large leaf area, which may have important implications for drought tolerance. Because of its tall, weak architecture, the plant commonly lodges under high fertility. The varieties showed variability in traits contributing to yield potential (such as panicle length, amount of grain, and leaf number on the tallest tiller) and other traits (such as leaf characteristics and internode length) that are important for varietal improvement programs (Table 1).

The study revealed that there was a lot of variation for grain yield. The majority of indigenous ghaiya varieties were at par with semidwarf rice variety Ghaiya 2 for grain yield (Table 2). At maturity, local farmers helped assess the phenotypic acceptance of the rice entries. They rated the majority of entries as good to excellent, with most of the entries having plant height and maturity periods suitable for local conditions.

The study identified variability between and within different genotypes that can be used both for developing varieties through pureline selection and in crossing programs. Although farmers are only growing these land races in a few places, more could be benefiting from them through participatory variety selection and promotion of them in similar ghaiya-growing areas.

To obtain varieties that are useful for farmers, indigenous knowledge and genetic resources must be tapped to develop high-yielding, suitable ghaiya varieties. ■

Table 2. Performance of Ghaiya varieties at Chyanglitar, Nepal (400 m). 1993-94.

Variety	1993			1994			Phenotypic acceptance 1-9
	Plant height (cm)	Days to maturity	Yield (t ha ⁻¹)	Plant height (cm)	Days to maturity	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)	
Kalo Basaune	148	116	3.1	157	124	4.1	3
Kalo Dhan	139	116	3.1	114	123	4.5	4
Sindure Ghaiya	141	116	3.5	143	122	5.4	3
Pahenle Ghaiya	132	113	3.6	142	120	3.6	4
Seto Ghaiya	135	120	3.7	155	123	3.6	4
Bichare	137	112	3.5	143	122	4.4	3
Chobo	132	114	3.4	133	118	3.9	4
Rato Ghaiya	136	117	3.4	144	122	4.5	3
Phalame Chobo	142	112	3.4	149	121	4.0	3
Sano Thantar	138	113	3.5	146	123	3.4	4
Nani Maiya	129	111	3.2	144	121	4.3	3
Pakhe Masino	139	115	3.4	152	124	4.5	3
Phalame Chobo	137	116	3.6	148	118	4.2	4
Nani Dhan	140	114	3.8	139	119	4.4	3
Langre	154	120	4.1	161	125	3.3	2
Jabaka	139	115	3.5	149	120	3.8	4
Begani	134	116	3.3	140	121	3.1	3
Dudhe Tauli	140	113	4.2	150	119	4.2	3
Dare Ghaiya	143	114	2.2	142	121	4.6	2
Chiuri	127	114	2.4	139	120	3.9	4
Jhyalebicharo	140	110	2.8	139	119	4.4	1
Jire Ghaiya	125	121	1.5	144	118	3.4	2
Linde Basaha	138	113	4.2	146	122	4.5	2
Ghaiya 2 (check)	77	125	2.6	85	117	4.9	3
Mean	133	115	2.89	142.9	120.9	4.1	3.08
LSD (0.05)	10.63	4.31	1.16	9.64	2.94	1.09	-

FKR33: a popular upland variety in Burkina Faso

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INERA scientists are developing new promising upland rice varieties from F₄ generations of pedigree lines screened at the Institut des Savanes research station in Bouaké, Côte d'Ivoire. The release of IRAT144 as FKR5 (Farako-Bâ Riz) in Burkina Faso was a result of this collaboration, but the variety has poor grain quality.

In 1982, we developed the line 1119-

5-2 by pedigree selection from the cross IRAT 112/IRAT 13. This variety was released as FKR33 in 1992.

FKR33 matures slightly earlier and is shorter than FKR5. Their grains are of the same length (9.8 mm), but FKR33 grains are more slender (2.8 mm) than that of FKR5 (3.0 mm).

Superior grain type and good head rice recovery are FKR33's best qualities. FKR33 produced 35% more grain than FKR5 in farmers' fields with less than 500 mm of rainfall. In trials conducted in 25 farmers' fields in Comoé Province in southwest Burkina Faso, FKR33's average yield was 3 t ha⁻¹. In Farako-Bâ its yield potential was 6 t ha⁻¹ during the wet season (see table). ■

Agronomic characteristics of upland rice varieties^a, Farako-Bâ Research Station, Burkina Faso. 1992.

Variety	Plant height (cm)	Maturity (d)	Panicles m ⁻² (no.)	Leaf blast ^b	Neck blast ^b	Grain yield (t ha ⁻¹)
FKR5 (IRAT144)	152	107	144	1	1	5.9
FKR33 (1195-5-2)	124	102	228	1	1	6.2
IREM194	162	105	268	3	1	5.9
IDSA13	134	105	128	1	1	5.5

^a Sowing date: 20 Jun 1992; fertilizer rate: 76-46-28 kg NPK ha⁻¹. ^b Scored using the Standard evaluation system for rice. IIRI 1988.